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Use of locoregional Perforator Flaps for reconstruction of lower limb defects: Our experience

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ABSTRACT:

BACKGROUND: Popularity of perforator flaps for lower limb reconstruction has increased due to multiple advantages. It gives replacement of tissues using 'like-by-like' principles.

METHODS: From December 2018 to January 2020, 11 cases of lower limb reconstruction were operated using perforator flaps. Outcome was assessed in view of age distribution, duration of surgery, hospital stay, postoperative complications, patient satisfaction & cosmesis.

RESULTS: Partial flap necrosis was noted as most common (three cases) postoperative complication in our study. Other complications were superficial epidermolysis, venous congestion & total flap loss which were managed conservatively except one case in which skin grafting was performed after debridement of totally necrosed flap.

CONCLUSIONS: Perforator flaps are having relatively simple surgical technique & advantage of less donor site morbidity. Identification of various perforators in lower limb makes its use more feasible for lower limb reconstruction.

KEY WORDS: - Perforator flaps, Lower limb reconstruction, locoregional

Introduction:

Koshima & Soeda first time used the term perforator flap for paraumbilical skin & fat island flap based on a muscular perforator in 1989. ⁽¹⁾ Hallock defines the perforator as any vessel that pierces through the fenestration in the deep fascia regardless of origin. ⁽²⁾ Perforator flap is defined as a vascularised tissue transfer based on a cutaneous perforator. (Direct or Indirect) ⁽³⁾ The increased popularity of perforator flaps has created a need for additional anatomical information regarding potential donor sites. ⁽⁴⁾

In our study we use different types of flaps based on different perforators for the reconstruction of lower limb defects.

Material & Methods:

From December 2018 to January 2020, we performed 11 cases of lower limb reconstruction using perforator flaps in our institute. All patients with small to medium sized defects were included in the study except cases in which features of injury to surrounding skin precluding the use of perforators adjacent to the defect were found. We also excluded the perforator based free flaps in this study. Informed written consent was taken in all cases prior to surgery.

Surgical Steps:

Preoperatively perforator was identified with 8 MHz hand held doppler probe on bedside which was confirmed with duplex imaging system. According to perforator location and defect size & location, planning & marking of flap was done.

Surgery was performed under tourniquet control & loupe magnification. Incision was taken on one side. Flap was elevated from that side & with meticulous dissection perforator was identified & dissected free from surrounding tissue. We can change our plan if we find better sized perforator. Till that we should try to preserve all perforators

identified during dissection. After confirmation & perforator dissection, flap elevation was completed. According to preoperative planning flap inset was given & donor site closure was performed.

Post operatively bandaging should be soft & light so as to avoid excessive compression to the flap with small window uncovered for monitoring of the flap. Post operatively all patients were evaluated for: 1. Operative time 2. Hospital stay 3. Postoperative complications like flap loss (Partial or Total), venous congestion or kinking superficial epidermolysis & hematoma.

Case 1:

25-year-old male patient with left medial malleolar defect with chronic osteomyelitis of ankle joint. We performed posterior tibial artery perforator-based V-Y advancement flap. Postoperatively partial flap loss was observed which was treated conservatively with dressing.

Pic 1: Preoperative defect & marking of perforator & flap

Pic 2: Intraoperative identification of perforator

Pic 3: Immediate Flap Inset

Case 2:

26-year-old male patient with post traumatic right calcaneal heel defect associated with exposure & injury to tendo achilles. We repaired tendo achilles & defect was covered with peroneal artery perforator-based propeller flap.

Pic 4: Preoperative defect

Pic 5: Intraoperative dissection of perforator

Pic 6: Follow up at 2 months

Case 3:

39-year-old male with post traumatic defect over left knee. LGAP (lateral genicular artery perforator) based propeller flap was performed. Superficial epidermolysis was noted postoperatively which was cured conservatively.

Pic 7: Preoperative defect

Pic 8: Intraoperative dissected perforator

Pic 9: 2 months follow up result**Results:**

Total Number of perforator flaps we performed was 11. Age distribution was between 20 to 60 years.

Average Operative time was 1.5 hours. Average hospital stay was 10.69≈11 days.

Etiology was trauma in 7 patients, Infection in 3 patients & benign naevus excision in 1 patient.

Total flap loss was observed in one patient of MSAP flap in which skin grafting was performed later.

Partial flap loss was observed in three patients may be due to infection. All cases were treated conservatively with dressing.

Venous congestion was observed in single case due to kinking in which repositioning & delayed inset was given & ultimately flap was survived without secondary surgery.

Superficial epidermolysis was noted in one patient who was treated conservatively with dressing.

Table 1. Age, Etiology, Flap type, Perforator & Complications

No.	Age	Etiology of defect	Type of flap	Perforator vessel	Complications
1	20	Trauma	Propeller	LGAP	--
2	60	Trauma	Transposition	ATAP	--
3	37	Trauma	Propeller	MSAP	Total Flap Necrosis
4	48	Infection	Propeller	LSAP	--
5	39	Trauma	Propeller	LGAP	Superficial epidermolysis

6	57	Infection	Transposition	ATAP	Partial flap necrosis
7	25	Benign naevus excision	V-Y Advancement	PTAP	--
8	42	Infection	Propeller	PAP	Venous congestion
9	26	Trauma	Propeller	PAP	Partial flap necrosis
10	40	Trauma	Propeller	PTAP	Venous congestion
11	25	Trauma	V-Y Advancement	PTAP	Partial flap necrosis

Discussion:

Perforator flaps evolved as reconstruction needed fine tuning while aiming to minimize donor morbidities. Advantages of the perforator flap are: 1. There is reduced donor site morbidity. 2. Versatility of design is there. 3. Muscle can be spared so functional deficit is less. 4. There is improved & fast post-operative recovery. Disadvantages are: 1. Meticulous dissection is needed to perform perforator flap which has steep learning curve. 2. As there is a need of meticulous dissection, operative time is increased. 3. There may be variability in the position & size of the perforators. ⁽⁵⁾

Perforasome theory was given by Saint-Cyr which states that 1. Each perforasome is linked with adjacent one. 2. Flap design & skin paddle orientation is based on direction of linking of vessels. 3. Filling of perforasome occurs with same source artery first f/b adjacent source arteries. 4. Mass vascularity of perforator adjacent to articulation is away from articulation. ⁽⁶⁾

Taylor and Palmer studied perforators closely & observed that there are many named perforating vessels to each angiosome of the body. ⁽⁷⁾ Anatomical understanding has laid the groundwork for the success of perforator flaps. Human body was divided into 61 vascular territories. There are approximately 400 cutaneous perforators to the skin, about 60% musculocutaneous & 40% septocutaneous. All flaps can be defined by source vessel on which the flap is based. Ex: ALT flap = LCFAP-vl. Suffix 's' is used if flap is based on septocutaneous perforator. ⁽⁸⁾

Propeller flap is a distinct entity which is defined as an Island flap that reaches the recipient site through axial rotation. In this perforator is dissected free from the fascial & fat adhesions to minimize kinking. It can be safely rotated upto 180 degrees. ⁽⁹⁾

In our study overall complication rate was 54.5% while Gir et al reported the overall complication rate of 25.8% & Innocenti et al noted an overall complication rate of 44%. It would appear that partial flap loss & venous congestion are two most common complications encountered. In our study partial flap loss was observed in three cases. Despite the complications, majority of perforator flaps were noted to survive, & secondary surgery is rarely required. ⁽¹⁰⁾ In our study over all flap survival rate was 90.9% which is comparable with Lazzeri et al in which it was 80.7%. ⁽¹¹⁾

Conclusion:

Perforator flaps are simply more flaps in armamentarium of the plastic surgeon. Good clinical judgment is still required to choose the best flap or a technique for a specific application. Perforator flaps are quicker to perform and with less donor site morbidity. The use of perforator flaps is new & exciting paradigm in reconstructive surgery.

References:

1. Koshima I, Soeda S. Inferior epigastric artery skin flaps without rectus abdominis muscle. *Br J Plast Surg.* 1989; 42:645.
2. Hallock GG. Direct and indirect perforator flaps: the history and controversey. *Plast Reconstr Surg.* 2003;111: 855-865, quiz 66.
3. Wei FC, Mardini S, authors. *Flaps and reconstructive surgery: Classification of flaps.* 2nd edition: Elsevier; 2017.
4. Geddes, C. R., Morris, S. F., and Neligan, P. C. *Perforator flaps: Evolution, classification, and applications.* *Ann. Plast. Surg.* 50: 90, 2003.
5. Neligan P. C., Gurtner G. C. authors. *Plastic surgery: Classification of flaps.* 4th edition: Elsevier; 2018: Vol 1; 379-381.
6. Saint-Cyr M, Wong C, Schavariem M, et al. The perforasome theory: vascular anatomy and clinical implications. *Plast Reconstr Surg.* 2009;124: 1529-1544.
7. Taylor GI, Palmer JH. The vascular territories (angiosomes) of the body: experimental study and clinical applications. *Br J Plast Surg.* 1987; 40:113-141.
8. Neligan P. C., Gurtner G. C. authors. *Plastic surgery: Vascular territories.* 4th edition: Elsevier; 2018: Vol 1; 361.
9. Teo TW. The propeller flap concept. *Clin Plast Surg.* 2010; 37: 615–626.
10. O-Wren Low, Sandeep J. Sebastian, Andre E. J. Cheah. A review of pedicled perforator flaps for reconstruction of the soft tissue defects of the leg and foot. *Indian J Plast Surg.* 52(1): 2636.
11. Lazzeri D, Huemer GM, Nicoli F, Larcher L, Dashti T, Grasseti L, Li Q, Zhang Y, Spinelli G, Agostini T. Indications, outcomes, and complications of pedicled propeller perforator flaps for upper body defects: a systemic review. *Arch Plast Surg* 2013; 40: 44-50. doi:10.5999/aps.2013.40.1.44.

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